

The Influence of Social Media Branding, E-WOM and Service Quality on Customer Loyalty through Customer Experience of Honda Brand Motorcycles Type of Automatic Scooter in Sidoarjo Regency, East Java

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ABSTRACT: Social media is not only a communication platform but also a space where consumers actively share their experiences regarding brands and products. This significantly influences consumer perceptions and purchase decisions. This study aims to analyze the influence of social media branding, E-WOM (electronic word-of-mouth), and service quality on customer loyalty through customer experiences with Honda automatic scooters in Sidoarjo, East Java. The population for this research consisted of an unknown number of Honda motorcycle customers in Sidoarjo, with a sample size determined to be 100 respondents using the Lemeshow formula. Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out using a Structural Equation Model (SEM) based on the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. Based on the analysis of 10 hypotheses, 6 were accepted while 4 were rejected. The findings indicate that, in direct effect, social media branding has a significantly positive influence customer experience, E-WOM does not significantly influence customer experience, and service quality has a significantly positive influence customer experience. Social media branding and customer experience significantly positively influence customer loyalty, while E-WOM and service quality do not significantly influence customer loyalty. Furthermore, in indirect effect, customer experience mediates the influence of social media branding and service quality on customer loyalty, but not the influence of E-WOM on customer loyalty.

KEYWORDS: social media branding, E-WOM, ser-qual, experience, loyalty

I. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly developing digital era, the role of social media in influencing brand image and interactions with customers is increasingly significant. Social media is not only a communication platform, but also a place where consumers actively share their experiences regarding brands and products. This influences consumer perceptions and purchasing decisions to a large extent. In Indonesia, the motorbike market, especially automatic scooters, continues to grow, with Honda as one of the main dominant brands, especially in Sidoarjo Regency, East Java, which has a significant motorized vehicle market.

Previous research shows that electronic Word-of-Mouth (E-WOM) plays an important role in shaping customer purchase intentions and loyalty. Consumer reviews and comments on social media can have a big impact on a brand's image. Negative e-WOM, such as widespread product controversies or issues on online platforms, can damage brand reputation and influence consumer purchasing preferences. The case of a broken ESAF frame on a Honda motorbike has become a major highlight on social media. The company's response to this crisis, including transparency and speed in responding to issues, has the potential to influence consumer perceptions of the brand's reliability in the future.

This study aims to fill the knowledge gap by focusing on the impact of negative E-WOM on consumer loyalty towards Honda in Sidoarjo Regency. The dealer's role in service quality management and crisis communication strategies on social media is the main focus, because an effective response can minimize the negative impact on brand image. A deep understanding of how social media influences consumer behavior and brand perception is a key aspect of modern marketing strategy. It is hoped that this study can provide new insights for companies, especially in facing communication challenges in the current digital era.

II. THEORETICAL STUDY

A. Marketing Management

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2021), marketing is a process in which companies engage customers, build strong customer relationships, and create customer value to capture value from customers in return.

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B. Social Media Branding

Social media branding is a crucial aspect of modern marketing strategy. Using social media platforms to build and manage a brand requires consistent and relevant content, active engagement with the audience, and the use of analytical data to continually refine the approach (Al-Abdallah et al., 2019).

C. Electronic Word-of-Mouth (e-WOM)

Electronic Word-of-Mouth (E-WOM) is a form of communication between consumers about products, services or brands via the internet and digital platforms. E-WOM messages are considered more influential if they are considered genuine and credible by the audience. Reviews from real consumers are often more trustworthy than official advertisements (Baker & King, 2022).

D. Service Quality

Good service quality can increase customer satisfaction and reduce the chances of customers switching to other brands. In the context of Honda motorbikes, quality service can create a positive experience for customers, which then influences customer loyalty. This theory argues that service quality is assessed based on a comparison between customer expectations and their perceptions of the service received. If perceptions exceed expectations, then customers will feel satisfied (Parasuraman & Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, 2018).

E. Customer Experience

Customer experience (CX) is the overall experience of customers during their interactions with a company or brand. CX covers every point of contact or touch a customer has with a business, from product purchase to after-sales support. This is an important concept because positive customer experiences can increase customer loyalty and influence future purchasing decisions (Meyer et al., 2007).

F. Organizational Commitment

Customer loyalty is the end result of positive interactions between customers and brands. Loyal customers tend to buy products or use services from the same brand repeatedly, even when they are faced with similar product or brand choices. According to Haryono and Albetris (2023), customer loyalty involves factors such as customer satisfaction, commitment to the brand, and perceived value.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

IV.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

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Regarding the research context, problem formulation, literature review, and conceptual framework, then hypothesis that can be formed is as follows:

- H1: Social media branding has a significant effect on customer experience for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.
- H2: Social media branding has a significant effect on customer loyalty for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.
- H3: E-WOM has a significant effect on customer experience for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.
- H4: E-WOM has a significant effect on customer loyalty for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.
- H5: Service quality has a significant effect on customer experience for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.
- H6: Service quality has a significant effect on customer loyalty for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.
- H7: Customer experience has a significant effect on customer loyalty for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.
- H8: Social media branding has a significant effect on customer loyalty mediated by Customer Experience, for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.
- H9: E-WOM has a significant effect on customer loyalty mediated by Customer Experience, for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.
- H10: Service quality has a significant effect on customer loyalty mediated by Customer Experience, for Honda brand automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency.

V. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Data Types and Sources

This research method is quantitative with an explanatory research approach, which aims to verify the hypothesis that has been determined by the researcher. This research uses primary data collected through questionnaires as the data collection tool.

B. Population

The population of this study were users of Honda brand motorbikes, automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency, East Java. The population in this study is the unknown number of Honda customers who use motorbikes in Sidoarjo. For the sample, use the Lemeshow method for an unknown population (Lemeshow, et al, 1990). How to calculate as follows:

$$n = \frac{z^2 \cdot P \cdot (1-P)}{d^2} = \frac{1,96^2 \cdot 0,5 \cdot (0,5)}{0,1^2} = \frac{0,9604}{0,1^2} = 96,04$$

Keterangan:

n = Number of Sampel

z = z-score at 95% confidence = 1.96

p = Maximum estimate

d = Error Rate

From the formula above, the sample size is determined using the Lemeshow formula with a maximum estimate of 50% and an error rate of 10%. For the sample in this study, it is rounded to 100.

C. Data Collection

The data collection technique used in this research is a survey with a questionnaire instrument. Respondents will be given a questionnaire containing questions regarding the variables studied, namely regarding the influence of social media branding, E-WOM and service quality on customer loyalty through the experience of using Honda brand motorbikes, automatic scooters in Sidoarjo Regency, East Java.

D. Data Analysis Method

Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out using a Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on Partial Least Square (PLS). PLS is a structural equation model (SEM) that is component or variance based. SEM is a field of statistical study that can test a series of relationships that are relatively difficult to measure simultaneously.

Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine whether or not there is an influence between research variables. This test is done by analyzing the Regression Weight value, namely the Critical Ratio (CR) and Probability (P) values. The required limits are ≥ 1.96 for the CR value and ≤ 0.05 for the P value. If the data processing results show a value that meets these requirements, then the proposed research hypothesis can be accepted.

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VI. RESULT & DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of Measurement Model/ Outer Model

Figure 2 Outer Model

To test convergent validity, Outer Loading and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) are utilized. An indicator is considered to meet convergent validity in the good category if the Outer Loading > 0.7 and the Average Variance Extracted > 0.5. The following are the Outer Loading and Average Variance Extracted for each indicator in this research variable:

Table 1 Convergent Validity Test - Outer Loading

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	
Social Media Branding (X1)	X1.1	0.810	
	X1.2	0.847	
	X1.4	0.778	
	X1.5	0.786	
	X1.6	0.885	
	X1.7	0.882	
	X1.8	0.859	
	X1.10	0.826	
	E-WOM (X2)	X2.1	0.849
		X2.2	0.799
X2.3		0.738	
X2.4		0.815	
X2.5		0.861	
X2.7		0.810	
X2.8		0.851	
X2.9		0.894	
X2.11		0.776	
Service Quality (X3)		X3.1	0.871
	X3.2	0.822	
	X3.3	0.859	
	X3.4	0.866	

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Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	
	X3.5	0.813	
	X3.6	0.828	
	X3.7	0.810	
	X3.8	0.718	
	X3.9	0.885	
	X3.10	0.888	
	X3.11	0.860	
	X3.12	0.796	
	Customer Experience (Z)	Z.1	0.865
		Z.2	0.881
		Z.3	0.830
		Z.4	0.847
Z.5		0.886	
Z.6		0.903	
Z.7		0.888	
Z.8		0.876	
Z.9		0.755	
Z.11		0.745	
Z.12		0.811	
Customer Loyalty (Y)		Y.1	0.730
	Y.3	0.777	
	Y.4	0.869	
	Y.5	0.896	
	Y.7	0.893	
	Y.8	0.882	
	Y.9	0.856	
	Y.10	0.828	
	Y.11	0.900	
	Y.12	0.816	

Source: Data processed by *Smart-PLS*

Based on the data shown in Table 1 Outer Loading, there are no indicator variables with outer loading values below 0.5. Therefore, all indicators are deemed appropriate or valid for use in the study and can be utilized for further analysis.

Table 2. Convergent Validity Test - Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Social Media Branding (X1)	0.684
E-WOM (X2)	0.677
Service Quality (X3)	0.699
Customer Experience (Z)	0.715
Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.716

Source: Data processed by *Smart-PLS*

Based on the data presented in Table 2, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all variables in this study are greater than 0.5. This indicates that each variable has good convergent validity.

In the following section, the results of discriminant validity testing will be discussed using Fornell-Larcker criteria and Cross Loading values. An indicator is considered to meet discriminant validity standards if its Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values are highest for its own variable compared to other variables. The Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values for each indicator are as follows:

Table 3. Discriminant Validity Test - Fornell-Larcker

	X1	X2	X3	Z	Y
Social Media Branding (X1)	0.827				
E-WOM (X2)	0.714	0.823			
Service Quality (X3)	0.593	0.688	0.836		
Customer Experience (Z)	0.696	0.670	0.809	0.846	
Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.505	0.539	0.711	0.706	0.860

Source: Data processed by *Smart-PLS*

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Table 4 .Discriminant Validity Test - Cross Loading

	SMB (X1)	E-WM (X2)	SQ (X3)	CE (Z)	CL (Y)
X1.1	0.810	0.570	0.504	0.523	0.358
X1.2	0.847	0.540	0.551	0.590	0.438
X1.4	0.778	0.687	0.562	0.585	0.368
X1.5	0.786	0.548	0.423	0.463	0.335
X1.6	0.885	0.699	0.486	0.552	0.440
X1.7	0.822	0.499	0.400	0.629	0.473
X1.8	0.859	0.506	0.426	0.551	0.395
X1.10	0.826	0.665	0.559	0.667	0.494
X2.1	0.693	0.849	0.497	0.554	0.408
X2.2	0.645	0.799	0.402	0.444	0.276
X2.3	0.455	0.738	0.619	0.471	0.404
X2.4	0.552	0.815	0.599	0.624	0.474
X2.5	0.623	0.861	0.704	0.621	0.516
X2.7	0.653	0.810	0.512	0.566	0.387
X2.8	0.541	0.851	0.545	0.551	0.461
X2.9	0.565	0.894	0.516	0.467	0.439
X2.11	0.559	0.776	0.624	0.591	0.545
X3.1	0.580	0.677	0.871	0.694	0.589
X3.2	0.447	0.647	0.822	0.615	0.522
X3.3	0.448	0.562	0.859	0.653	0.603
X3.4	0.454	0.537	0.866	0.700	0.658
X3.5	0.415	0.547	0.813	0.575	0.578
X3.6	0.467	0.532	0.828	0.576	0.512
X3.7	0.593	0.474	0.810	0.720	0.597
X3.8	0.573	0.527	0.718	0.675	0.541
X3.9	0.491	0.586	0.885	0.719	0.700
X3.10	0.664	0.740	0.888	0.799	0.645
X3.11	0.484	0.552	0.860	0.729	0.629
X3.12	0.280	0.507	0.796	0.605	0.516
Z.1	0.530	0.447	0.715	0.865	0.775
Z.2	0.468	0.589	0.722	0.881	0.819
Z.3	0.535	0.571	0.682	0.830	0.726
Z.4	0.504	0.431	0.656	0.847	0.776
Z.5	0.588	0.685	0.830	0.886	0.824
Z.6	0.647	0.596	0.718	0.903	0.793
Z.7	0.661	0.634	0.754	0.888	0.748
Z.8	0.571	0.529	0.671	0.876	0.722
Z.9	0.710	0.597	0.498	0.755	0.490
Z.11	0.719	0.601	0.531	0.745	0.519
Z.12	0.618	0.568	0.679	0.811	0.721
Y.1	0.481	0.432	0.571	0.592	0.730
Y.3	0.270	0.363	0.444	0.638	0.777
Y.4	0.380	0.380	0.629	0.765	0.869
Y.5	0.450	0.477	0.568	0.687	0.896
Y.7	0.365	0.318	0.609	0.762	0.893
Y.8	0.551	0.560	0.677	0.788	0.882
Y.9	0.480	0.611	0.649	0.798	0.856
Y.10	0.392	0.848	0.648	0.752	0.828
Y.11	0.454	0.543	0.634	0.761	0.900
Y.12	0.460	0.379	0.566	0.694	0.816

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Tables 3 and 4, it is evident that each indicator has the highest Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values for its respective variable compared to other variables. This indicates that the indicators used in this study possess good discriminant validity for constructing their respective variables.

This section will present the results of reliability testing using composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha values. An indicator is considered to meet reliability standards if the composite reliability values exceed 0.6 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1998; Chin &

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Dibbern, 2010), and if the rho_A and Cronbach's alpha values are greater than 0.7 (Vinzi, Trinchera, & Amato, 2010). The following are the composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha values for each indicator:

Table 5. Reliability Test - Composite Reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Composite Reliability	Rho_A	Cronbach's Alpha
Social Media Branding (X1)	0.945	0.938	0.934
E-WOM (X2)	0.949	0.944	0.940
Service Quality (X3)	0.965	0.963	0.961
Customer Experience (Z)	0.965	0.964	0.960
Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.962	0.959	0.955

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Table 5, it is clear that the composite reliability values for all research variables exceed 0.6, and the values for rho_A and Cronbach's alpha are above 0.7. These findings demonstrate that each variable meets the criteria for composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha. Consequently, it can be concluded that the variables exhibit a high level of reliability.

A. Evaluation of Structural Model/ Inner Model

Figure 3 Inner Model

Path coefficient evaluation is used to indicate the strength of the effect or influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Based on the inner model diagram displayed in Figure 3, it can be explained that the highest path coefficient value is the effect of Customer Experience on Customer Loyalty, which is 7.368. This is followed by the effect of Service Quality on Customer Experience, which is 7.253, while the smallest effect is E-WOM on Customer Loyalty, which is 0.008. These results show that all variables in this model have positive path coefficient values. This indicates that the larger the path coefficient value of an exogenous variable on an endogenous variable, the stronger its influence.

Table 6. R-Square

	R-Square
Customer Experience (Z)	0,758
Customer Loyalty (Y)	0,727

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Table 6, the R-Square values for the Customer Experience and Customer Loyalty variables are 0.758 and 0.727, respectively. This indicates that the exogenous variables explain 75.8% (Strong) and 72.7% (Strong) of the variation in the endogenous variables. The remaining 24.2% and 27.3% are due to the influence of other exogenous variables not measured in this study.

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Table 7. Path Coefficient - Direct Effect

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Signification
Social Media Branding (X1) → Customer Experience (Z)	0.320	0.317	0.082	3.894	0.000	Significant
Social Media Branding (X1) → Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.185	0.172	0.069	2.657	0.008	Significant
E-WOM (X2) → Customer Experience (Z)	0.029	0.038	0.079	0.367	0.714	Not Significant
E-WOM (X2) → Customer Loyalty (Y)	-0.001	0.005	0.110	0.008	0.994	Not Significant
Service Quality (X3) → Customer Experience (Z)	0.599	0.592	0.083	7.253	0.000	Significant
Service Quality (X3) → Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.062	0.072	0.129	0.480	0.632	Not Significant
Customer Experience (Z) → Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.939	0.916	0.127	7.368	0.000	Significant

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Table 8. Path Coefficients - Indirect Effect

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Signification
Social Media Branding (X1) → Customer Experience (Z) → Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.301	0.294	0.097	3.102	0.002	Significant
E-WOM (X2) → Customer Experience (Z) → Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.027	0.034	0.072	0.376	0.707	Not Significant
Service Quality (X3) → Customer Experience (Z) → Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.563	0.537	0.080	7.023	0.000	Significant

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Tables 7 and 8 present the results of the PLS calculation, indicating the influence between variables. From the data, it is evident that out of the 10 hypotheses tested in this research, a hypothesis is considered accepted or significant if the P-Values are less than 0.05. Four hypotheses indicate an insignificant effect, while the remaining six hypotheses show a significant effect. Below is an in-depth analysis of the influence between variables according to the proposed hypotheses:

H1: Social media branding influences customer experience.

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the relationship between social media branding and customer experience shows the Original Sample (O) result, namely 0.320, stating that these two variables have a positive relationship, with a t-statistic of 3.894 which meets the t-statistics standard > 1.96 , so it can be concluded that the first hypothesis in this research is accepted and significant. The interpretation of these results is that Honda's efforts in utilizing social media platforms to strengthen their brand effectively improve customer experience. This shows that the content published, interactions carried out, and campaigns run on social media have succeeded in creating a positive impression and increasing customer satisfaction with their automatic scooter motorbike products. Overall, these findings emphasize the importance of social media branding as a strategic tool in establishing and maintaining positive customer experiences, even in the face of attacks from competitors. Honda can continue to optimize the use of social media to support their marketing strategy, with a focus on transparent communication, meaningful interactions, and content that highlights the strengths of their products, in order to maintain and increase customer satisfaction and loyalty in Sidoarjo Regency. This shows that there is a positive and significant influence of social media branding on customer experience for Honda automatic motorbike users in Sidoarjo Regency. The higher the social media branding, the higher the customer experience. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Cemre Serbetcioglu, and Aysu Göçer (2022), Niels Frederik Lund, Scott A. Cohen, and Caroline Scarles (2017).

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H2: Social media branding influences customer loyalty.

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the relationship between social media branding and Customer Loyalty shows the Original Sample (O) result, namely 0.185, stating that these two variables have a positive relationship, with a t-statistic of 2.657 which meets the t-statistics standard > 1.96 , so it can be concluded that the second hypothesis in this research is accepted and significant. The interpretation of these results is that companies' efforts to effectively utilize social media platforms to strengthen their brands can increase customer loyalty. This means that the content published, interactions carried out, and campaigns run on social media are able to create a deep positive impression and increase customer loyalty to the company's products or services. In this context, companies' use of social media is not just about promoting products or services, but also about building closer relationships with customers. By presenting interesting, informative and relevant content, and by interacting directly with customers, companies can create strong emotional bonds. This allows customers to feel closer and more connected to the brand, which in turn increases their loyalty. This shows that there is a positive and significant influence of social media branding on Customer Loyalty among Honda automatic motorbike users in Sidoarjo Regency. The higher the social media branding, the higher the customer loyalty. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Mayank Yadav, Zillur Rahman (2018).

H3: E-WOM influences customer experience.

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the relationship between E-WOM and customer experience shows the Original Sample (O) results, namely 0.029, stating that these two variables have a positive relationship, with a t-statistic of 0.367 which does not meet the standard of t-statistics < 1.96 , so it can be concluded that the third hypothesis in this study is rejected and is not significant. Hypothetical results showing that electronic word-of-mouth (E-WOM) has no significant effect on customer experience provide interesting insights for companies' digital marketing strategies. This means that although online recommendations and reviews from other users are often considered important in shaping user perceptions and experiences, in certain contexts, their influence on customer experience is not as strong or significant. There are several factors that can explain why E-WOM tends not to have a significant effect on customer experience. Trust in branding on social media can be greater than with E-WOM. An effective branding strategy on social media, including engaging, informative and interactive content, can more powerfully shape the customer experience. Official content from a brand that is presented consistently and interestingly can create a deeper positive impression. For example, Honda can utilize social media to showcase the quality of their products, the latest innovations, and customer satisfaction, which can help overcome criticism or attacks from competitors. The results of this research are not in line with the results of previous research by I Wayan Suartina, et al. (2022).

H4: E-WOM influences customer loyalty.

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the relationship between E-WOM and Customer Loyalty shows the Original Sample (O) results, namely -0.001, indicating that these two variables have a negative relationship, with t-statistics of 0.008, which does not meet the t-statistics standard < 1.96 . So it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis in this study is rejected and is not significant. Hypothetical results indicating that electronic word-of-mouth (E-WOM) does not have a significant impact on customer loyalty provide important insights for companies' digital marketing strategies. This suggests that although online reviews and recommendations are often considered crucial in influencing purchasing decisions and customer loyalty, in some situations, their influence is not as great as one might think. Direct customer experience is often more influential than E-WOM. Customers tend to rely on their personal experience with a product or service as a key indicator of their satisfaction and loyalty. If their experience with the product has been positive or negative, E-WOM is likely not strong enough to change their perception and loyalty. In this case, direct experience provides a stronger basis for customers to judge product quality and performance and form their loyalty. The results of this research are not in line with the results of previous research by Bagyalakshmi Gopi and Nusrah Samat (2020).

H5: Service quality influences customer experience.

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the relationship between service quality and customer experience shows the Original Sample (O) results, namely 0.599, indicating that these two variables have a positive relationship, with a t-statistic of 7.253 which meets the standard of t-statistics > 1.96 , so it can be concluded that the fifth hypothesis in this study was accepted and significant. These results indicate that the company's efforts to provide superior service can effectively improve the overall customer experience. This suggests that service quality aspects such as speed, friendliness, reliability and staff expertise play a crucial role in forming a positive impression and increasing customer satisfaction levels. This shows that there is a positive and significant influence of Service Quality on the customer experience of Honda automatic motorbike users in Sidoarjo Regency. The higher the service quality, the higher the customer experience. The results of this research are in line with the results of previous research by Endang Tjahjaningsih (2021). The strategy to improve service quality is an important strategic step for Honda in facing fierce competition in the automotive industry. By prioritizing customer experience through exceptional service, Honda can not only overcome challenges from competitors, but also build a strong foundation for long-term growth and continued customer loyalty.

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H6: Service quality influences customer loyalty.

Based on the results of the statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the relationship between Service Quality and Customer Loyalty shows the Original Sample (O) results, namely 0.062, stating that these two variables have a positive relationship, with a t-statistic of 0.480, which does not meet the standard of t-statistics < 1.96 , so it can be It was concluded that the sixth hypothesis in this study was rejected and was not significant. These results are not in line with research by Bagyalakshmi Gopi and Nusrah Samat (2020), the higher the Service Quality, the higher the Customer Loyalty. Although good service quality is expected to increase customer loyalty, in the case of attacks aimed at Honda automatic frames that are considered fragile by competing brands, Honda's response to this criticism may not be entirely determined by service improvements alone. Other factors such as perception of product quality, price, and brand trust also play a crucial role in determining customer loyalty. Although Honda may improve their after-sales service in response to such criticism, customers may still consider other options if they believe that competing brands' products offer better quality or more competitive prices. This shows that in responding to attacks from competitors, companies need to consider various factors that can influence customer perceptions and decisions. The emotional experience and personal connection built between customers and brands also play an important role in maintaining loyalty. Customers who feel a strong emotional attachment to Honda may be more likely to remain loyal, even though they may be aware of criticism of certain aspects of its products. Therefore, Honda needs to not only improve service quality, but also strengthen emotional relationships with customers through marketing strategies that prioritize brand values and the positive experiences provided to customers.

H7: Customer experience influences customer loyalty.

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the relationship between customer experience and customer loyalty shows the Original Sample (O) results, namely 0.939, stating that these two variables have a positive relationship, with a t-statistic of 7.368 which meets the t-statistics standard > 1.96 , so it can be It was concluded that the seventh hypothesis in this study was accepted and significant. This shows that there is a positive and significant influence of customer loyalty on the customer experience of Honda automatic motorbike users in Sidoarjo Regency. The higher the customer loyalty, the higher the customer experience. The results of this research are in line with previous research by Sanja Pekovic and Sylvie Rolland (2020). The hypothesis results which show that customer experience has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty provide important insights for the company's marketing strategy and customer relationship management which have deep implications in facing challenges such as attacks directed by competing brands on Honda's automatic frame which is considered fragile. In this situation, Honda's response to this criticism included not only improving product quality, but also focusing on improving the overall customer experience. High quality after-sales service, including fast, friendly and competent service in workshops, as well as ease in the process of repairing or maintaining motorbikes, can significantly increase customer satisfaction. This positive experience not only makes customers feel appreciated and satisfied with the service they receive, but also builds strong trust and loyalty to the Honda brand. For example, customers who experience efficient, high-quality service at a Honda repair shop are likely to return for subsequent service and even recommend it to others, despite criticism of the quality of certain parts.

H8: Social media branding influences customer loyalty mediated by Customer Experience

From table 5.17 above, it can be seen that the original sample value (O) is 0.301, which states that the three variables have a positive influence. Then by looking at the P-Values value of 0.002, which is below 0.05 and the significance value or t-statistics is $3.102 > 1.96$ (greater than 1.96). The P-Values and t-statistics values indicate that social media branding (X1) influences customer loyalty (Y) with customer experience (Z) as a mediator. Based on the regression results, it can be concluded that the eighth hypothesis is accepted and significant. In these results, the influence of the mediating variable, namely customer experience, is Partial Mediation. Partial mediation means that the presence of a mediating variable does not change the results of the exogenous variable in influencing the endogenous variable, so that in the presence or absence of customer experience, social media branding can influence customer loyalty. The hypothesis results which confirm that social media branding has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty with customer experience as a mediator provide in-depth insight into how the complex interaction between branding on social media, customer experience, and customer loyalty can play a role in facing challenges such as attacks by competing brands on spare parts. Honda's automatic is considered fragile. The interpretation of these findings suggests that effective branding strategies on social media not only build brand awareness but also play an important role in shaping positive customer experiences, which in turn increases loyalty levels.

H9: E-WOM influences customer loyalty mediated by Customer Experience

From table 5.17 above, it can be seen that the original sample value (O) is 0.027, which states that the three variables have a positive influence. Then by looking at the P-Values value of 0.707, which is above 0.05 and the significance value or t-statistics is $0.376 < 1.96$ (smaller than 1.96). The P-Values and t-statistics values indicate that E-WOM (X2) has no effect on customer loyalty (Y) with customer experience (Z) as a mediator. Based on the regression results, it can be concluded that the ninth hypothesis is rejected and is not significant. In these results, the influence of the mediating variable, namely customer experience, is No Mediation. No mediation means that the presence of mediating variables cannot change the results of exogenous variables in influencing

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endogenous variables, so that customer experience cannot increase the influence of E-WOM on customer loyalty. Hypothetical results showing that electronic word-of-mouth (E-WOM) has no significant effect on customer loyalty, with customer experience as a mediating variable, provide important insight into the complexity of factors that influence loyalty in a digital context. Although E-WOM is often considered a potential factor in influencing customer perceptions and purchasing decisions, in some cases, its influence on customer loyalty may not be as strong as expected. Factors such as the credibility of the E-WOM source, direct customer experience with the brand, and competitive dynamics can moderate the impact of E-WOM on consumer purchasing behavior.

H10: Service quality influences customer loyalty mediated by Customer Experience

From table 5.17 above, it can be seen that the original sample value (O) is 0.563, which states that the three variables have a positive influence. Then by looking at the P-Values value of 0.000, which is below 0.05 and the significance value or t-statistics is $7.023 > 1.96$ (greater than 1.96). The P-Values and t-statistics values indicate that Service Quality (X3) influences customer loyalty (Y) with customer experience (Z) as a mediator. Based on the regression results, it can be concluded that the tenth hypothesis is accepted and significant. In these results, the influence of the mediating variable, namely customer experience, is Full Mediation. What is meant by full mediation is that the presence of mediating variables can change the results of exogenous variables in influencing endogenous variables, so that the presence of customer experience as a mediating variable is very necessary so that service quality can influence customer loyalty. These results highlight that high service quality has a significant impact on customer loyalty through customer experience as the main mediator in this relationship. In the context of the automotive industry, a phenomenon occurs that shows how important product integrity and responsibility are in maintaining customer trust. The case of a competitor brand's attack on fragile Honda automatic spare parts provides a deep understanding of how product reliability and company response can influence customer perceptions. For example, at the Honda service workshop in Sidoarjo Regency, implementing best practices in providing efficient, friendly and responsive service to customer needs is a key factor in creating a positive customer experience. Well-trained staff not only completes repairs in a timely manner but also builds strong personal relationships with customers, significantly increasing their satisfaction. Positive customer experiences not only build satisfaction but also strengthen brand loyalty. When customers feel they are treated well and their needs are consistently met, this creates a strong emotional bond and increases trust in the Honda brand.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study examines the impact of social media branding, E-WOM, and service quality on customer loyalty, with customer experience as a mediating variable. The findings indicate that social media branding significantly influences customer experience and customer loyalty among Honda matic motorcycle customers in Sidoarjo. Service quality also has a significant effect on customer experience but not on customer loyalty. E-WOM does not significantly impact either customer experience or customer loyalty. Additionally, customer experience significantly affects customer loyalty. When considering customer experience as a mediating variable, social media branding and service quality significantly influence customer loyalty, while E-WOM does not.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are suggestions from the author for further research based on our research results.

1. Strengthen Social Media Branding Strategies: Focus on creating engaging content to enhance customer experience and loyalty.
2. Increase Trust in Reviews: Although E-WOM did not show significant effects, actively manage testimonials to build trust.
3. Maintain and Improve Service Quality: In addition to maintaining service quality, explore other factors such as incentive programs that may influence customer loyalty.
4. Expand Research Scope: Include additional variables such as customer demographics, analyze different social media platforms, and consider offline promotions. Conduct longitudinal studies to understand the long-term effects on customer experience and customer loyalty.

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